

MULTI-SCALE MODELLING OF POLYMER COMPOSITE MATERIALS UNDER BLAST AND BALLISTIC LOADING

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Keywords: *micro, meso, macro, multi-scale, blast, high-strain-rate, composite*

1.0 Introduction

In the present work the behavior of composites at multiple scales is considered where the micro, meso and macro scales are defined as follows. At the micro scale, fibres are embedded in a matrix material to form a yarn or tow i.e. a fibre bundle. At the meso scale, yarns are arranged in a desired architecture, e.g. non-crimped or plain weave, and embedded in the matrix material. At the macro scale, several meso scale laminae, comprising a repeated yarn structure, are stacked to form a composite laminate.

Fig 1. (a) Micro, (b) Meso and (c) Macro Scale. Not to scale.

The micro scale geometry, as shown in Fig. 1(a), consists of unidirectional S2 glass or carbon fibres, surrounded by a thin interface layer, idealised in a hexagonal packing arrangement and embedded in an epoxy matrix. The meso scale geometry, as shown in Fig. 1(b), consists of four S2 glass or carbon yarns in a balanced 0/90 NCF (Non Crimped Fabric) arrangement, again all embedded in the epoxy matrix. The material being analyzed at the macro scale is a hybrid S2 glass/carbon epoxy composite laminate. The laminate comprises plies of non-crimped fabric orientated at either 0/90 or +/-45 in a

balanced layup and incorporated into a multi-layered/multi-material blast mitigation structure as shown in Fig. 1(c). This structure has a front face of steel and the composite laminate on the rear face.

The aim of this work is to simulate a blast and ballistic event on the macro scale model. The high strain rate properties for the composite layer of the structure are provided by micro and meso simulations.

This predictive modelling approach aims to replace the macro scale material experimental characterisation, which can be time consuming, multifaceted, in terms of using numerous different strain rate test procedures and equipment, and often prohibitively expensive. An extensive experimental programme of this kind was conducted by Brown *et al* [1] for E-glass/polypropylene woven fabric with the aim of providing input properties for the material subroutine MAT162 in LS-DYNA. The techniques for experimental high strain rate testing, as well as information on the strain rate dependence of the mechanical properties of composite materials are detailed in reviews by Walley *et al* [2], Hamouda and Hashmi [3], Jacob *et al* [4] and Sierakowski [5].

A multi-scale modelling approach, with the aim of complementing, and ultimately, replacing experimental tests for material characterisation, has been described by Ernst *et al* [6]. This approach took into account the progressive failure in a glass/epoxy textile composite at the micro, meso and macro scales. The numerical results compared well with experimental results at quasi-static test rates. Strain rate dependence, however, was not considered

in this study. This is a key feature of the work described herein.

2.0 Micro / Meso Modelling Methodology

All micro and meso scale modelling has been performed in ABAQUS Explicit. PYTHON scripting has been utilized for automated simulation definition, including the generation of unit cell geometry and the application of periodic boundary conditions based on translational symmetry. FORTRAN programming has also been utilised to define material behavior for all constituents in an ABAQUS VUMAT explicit subroutine.

2.1 Material Models

Matrix and interfaces are defined as elastic isotropic up to the point of failure, whereas fibres and yarns are defined as elastic transversely isotropic up to the point of failure. Damage in the matrix and yarns is initiated by the maximum stress criterion. Damage in the fibre is initiated when the stress in the fibre direction is greater than the tensile/compressive strength of the fibre, depending on the loading. Damage in the interface is initiated when the shear stress in the direction along the fibre length reaches the interfacial shear strength. Elastic, failure and damage properties of the resin and fibres are obtained from a combination of in-house experimental test data and published data [7].

Following damage initiation in the fibre and interface, elements are immediately deleted from the analysis to simulate brittle fracture. Following damage initiation in the matrix and yarns, the damage is allowed to evolve through degradation of the stiffness at a defined rate which can be set to produce a post failure response ranging from brittle to ductile. This is followed by element deletion at a maximum damage level.

The material subroutines for all constituents, except the fibres, incorporates strain rate scaling of stiffness and strength based on a logarithmic scaling law.

2.2 Simulations

Simulations for the micro scale model have been tested separately with S2 glass fibres and carbon fibres, both subjected to nine loading conditions (longitudinal tension/compression, two transverse directions in tension/compression and three shear

cases). Each loading condition has been tested over a range of strain rates (1, 1000 and 10000 s⁻¹). Analysis of these tests provides material properties for a unidirectional S2 glass yarn/tow and a carbon yarn/tow at the meso scale.

The meso scale model simulations were also run separately with S2 glass yarns and carbon yarns. At this level, the models were subjected to seven loading conditions (in plane tension/compression, through thickness tension/compression and three shear cases). Again, each loading condition was run over a range of strain rates (100 and 1000 s⁻¹). Analysis of these simulation results provides material properties for the S2 glass 0/90 NCF layers and carbon 0/90 NCF layers making up the macro scale composite layer in the blast and ballistic structures. These 0/90 NCF layer properties can be orientated at the macro scale to provide the properties for the +/- 45 NCF layers as required.

3.0 Micro / Meso Results

In the following section selected examples of the micro/meso results are detailed. The results are not presented in their entirety due to the large number of loading conditions, strain rates and materials tested.

3.1 Micro Results

Fig.2. Example stress strain curves for S2 glass / epoxy micro unit cell in transverse tension and longitudinal tension at 1 (light grey), 1000 (dark grey) and 10000 (black) /s. Magnitudes omitted for proprietary reasons.

Figure 2 shows the results of testing the S2 glass/epoxy micro unit cell in transverse and longitudinal tension at three strain rates. Transverse tension, at all three strain rates, shows elastic behaviour and strain softening as a result of matrix damage accumulation. The elastic and damage phases are both clearly strain rate sensitive and the

increase in stiffness and strength with increasing strain rate can be seen under transverse tension. This strain rate effect, however, is not observed in the longitudinal tension results, also shown in Figure 2. This is due to the fact that, under this loading condition, fibre dominated failure occurs and the fibres exhibit no strain rate dependency. The matrix damage initiation can be represented in the material model by the Maximum Stress criterion, Figure 3(a). The explicit material subroutine reduces the stiffness of the damaged elements at a defined rate. For the matrix, this rate is very slow to reflect a ductile response and produces the gradual reduction in stress at the higher values of strain. Fibres are modelled as isotropic, elastic-to-failure at the tensile fibre strength. The material subroutine then deletes the failed fibre elements from the analysis, displaying abrupt brittle failure.

The progression of damage in the S2 glass/epoxy micro unit cell in transverse tension is shown in Figure 3. The transverse loading direction in this case is horizontally across the page. The damage initiates horizontally between the fibres and then starts to grow vertically from one row of fibres to the next. Eventually at the larger strains the damage evolves into a ‘crack’ across the entire height of the unit cell.

Fig.3. Example of damage progression in S2 glass / epoxy micro unit cell in transverse (horizontal) tension at 10000 /s. At (a) 4%, (b) 6% and (c) 10% strain. 0.0 indicates no damage. 1.0 indicates maximum damage.

All the micro testing for S2 glass and carbon is condensed into properties that are carried forward for use as meso scale S2 glass and carbon yarn properties. The following parameters are obtained from the stress strain curves; stiffness values, Poisson’s ratio values, strengths, strain softening parameters (controls the rate of stiffness degradation after damage initiation) and strain rate scaling constants for stiffness and strength.

3.2 Meso Results

Figure 4 shows the results of testing the S2 glass/epoxy meso unit cell in in-plane tension and through thickness tension at two strain rates. The in-plane tension results, at both strain rates, show an initial linear increase in stress with increasing strain i.e. the elastic region. The curve then exhibits a ‘knee’ point, where the modulus is reduced. The curve then continues at this reduced modulus until a maximum stress is reached where the stress sharply drops to zero. The ‘knee’ point in the curve arises due to damage initiation in the yarns transverse to the loading direction, as shown in Figure 5(a). The final sharp drop off in stress to zero occurs due to final brittle failure of the yarns parallel to the loading direction; Figure 5(c).

The stress strain curve for through thickness tension shows a linear increase in stress with increasing strain in the elastic region. The stress then reaches a maximum before falling off. The maximum stress point occurs when the through thickness stress exceeds the through thickness strength of the yarns. The matrix then continues to damage as it takes up the load causing the gradual reduction in stress after the initial sharp drop off.

Fig.4. Example stress strain curves for S2 glass / epoxy meso unit cell in in-plane tension and through thickness tension at 100 (grey) and 1000 (black) /s. Magnitudes omitted for proprietary reasons.

The progression of damage in the S2 glass/epoxy meso unit cell under in-plane tension is shown in Figure 5. The damage initiates in the edges of the transverse yarns, Figure 5(a). The damage then spreads throughout the entirety of the transverse yarns and into the nearby surrounding resin, Figure 5(b). At some point after this the stress in the yarns parallel to the loading direction reaches their tensile strength and final failure occurs, Figure 5(c).

All the meso testing for S2 glass and carbon is condensed into properties that are carried forward for use as macro scale S2 glass 0/90 NCF lamina properties and carbon 0/90 NCF lamina properties. The macro scale modelling is conducted in LS-DYNA and uses proprietary material models as described in sections 4 and 5 of this paper. The material cards for these material models are completed from the above meso scale modelling results.

Fig.5. Example of damage progression in S2 glass / epoxy meso unit cell in in-plane (top left to bottom right direction) tension at 1000 /s. At (a) 4.5%, (b) 8% and (c) 9.3% strain. 0.0 indicates no damage. 1.0 indicates maximum damage.

3.3 Validation

The predicted yarn stiffness (longitudinal and transverse) values from the micro simulations compare well to Rule of Mixtures analytical predictions using fibre stiffness and strain rate scaled matrix stiffness properties.

The predicted in-plane tensile stiffness and strength values from the meso scale simulations compare well to internal data from BAE Systems experimental testing (low, intermediate and high strain rate).

4.0 Blast Panel Case Study (BAE SYSTEMS)

4.1 Description

Simulation of a preliminary armour design concept has been undertaken to assess the response to blast load and to compare results with tests undertaken in

the early phases of the LiMBS (Lightweight Materials and Structures for Blast and Ballistic Survivability) project.

The configuration of the test is shown in Figure 6. The 800mm x 800mm test panel is clamped by through-bolts to a rigid steel framework. Blast loading is applied to the upper surface from a 2 kg pancake charge of PE4, offset from the upper surface by 150mm. The panel is comprised of two materials; a toughened steel front face (ArmoX 340) and an S2 glass/carbon composite laminate behind. The two layers of material are held together by the clamping force imposed by the rig.

Fig.6. Panel blast test setup

4.2 Modelling Approach

Numerical simulations were performed using LS-DYNA. The extent of the finite element model is shown in Figure 7 (quarter symmetry employed).

Fig.7. Model Setup with detail of panel section

Single point integration hexahedral elements were employed throughout the model, each ply of the carbon/S2-glass laminate being represented as a single layer of elements. MAT_COMPOSITE_MSC (MAT162) was used to describe the rate dependant behaviour of the carbon and S2 glass materials. These material models were populated with data supplied from micro/meso-scale modelling. Tiebreak

interfaces were defined between the adjacent laminate layers with failure parameters specified to represent delamination.

The panel was loaded directly with pressure histories derived from a preliminary 2-D axisymmetric Euler analysis of the detonation of the 2kg pancake charge.

4.3 Simulation Results

The level of predicted damage to the panel is shown in Figure 8, alongside the post-test panel.

Fig.8. Panel damage, model and post-test

Post-test damage in the laminate is characterized by significant intra-lamina failure and gross delamination, with bulging deformation, but no penetration, of the steel front face. The model predicts a similar pattern of failure in the composite, combining fibre and matrix in-plane failure with delamination across the majority of the panel. The model also shows good agreement with data from timing pins positioned behind the test panel (recording the time at specific levels of panel displacement). In addition, the overall deformation level of the front steel face is closely aligned to the deformation measured in test.

The overall results provide confidence in the modelling approach and material data employed to simulate this blast event. The techniques established have provided the means to move forward with the assessment of alternative blast configurations to support the development of lightweight, multi-material armour concepts.

5.0 Ballistic Panel Case Study (QinetiQ)

Building upon work undertaken in support of the Europa CAFV project [8], QinetiQ are currently investigating the use of multi-scale modelling as a means of predicting the ballistic and spall liner performance of structural composites. The resistance of 24mm thick hybrid S2 glass / Carbon

laminates to perforation by 12.7mm fragment simulating projectiles (FSP) was initially assessed experimentally to determine the V_{50} ballistic limit, which defines the impact speed at which 50% of projectiles would be expected to perforate the target. For the baseline 24mm thick S2 glass / carbon hybrid considered under the LiMBS project, a ballistic limit velocity of 646m/s was obtained.

5.1 Ballistic Impact Model Description

Numerical modeling of the fragment impact tests was undertaken in LS-DYNA using MAT_COMPOSITE_SOLID_FAILURE (MAT59) to represent the hybrid composite target. Using the mesoscale modelling data, the 24mm thick quasi-isotropic laminate was divided into 28 layers of elements, with each layer representing two plies of the physical laminate and with fibres running in the 0 and 90 or +45 and -45 directions. Given the strain rate dependent nature of the material properties derived from the micro and meso scale models, and in the absence of strain rate dependency within MAT59, initial simulations have used quasi-static material property data to represent the glass and carbon reinforced layers of the hybrid composite laminate.

The 12.7mm FSP was represented as a right circular AISI 4340 steel cylinder using MAT_JOHNSON_COOK (MAT15) and EOS_GRUNIESEN. Contact between the projectile and target was achieved using an eroding contact algorithm, with erosion added to the composite material model to delete severely distorted elements from the simulation.

5.2 Ballistic Impact Modelling Results

The ballistic impact model was run for a series of increasing impact velocities to determine the predicted performance limit of the hybrid composite target. Figure 9 illustrates the model for a fragment impact velocity of 600 m/s, while the projectile's velocity history is shown in Figure 10.

The results obtained from the initial ballistic impact models indicate that, using quasi-static material property data, the model under-predicts the resistance of the hybrid composite target to fragment perforation. To a large extent, this is to be expected, with both the S2 glass and carbon meso-scale

models reporting an appreciable level of strain rate sensitivity.

Fig.9. Ballistic impact model representing impact of 12.7mm FSP on 24mm thick hybrid glass / carbon target at 600m/s

Fig.10. Predicted velocity history for 12.7mm FSP impacting 24mm thick hybrid glass / carbon target at 600m/s

Future work under the LiMBS project will investigate the use of high strain rate property data as a means of improving the predictive capability of the ballistic impact model, the effect of through thickness reinforcement on the development of damage within the target, and the ability of numerical modelling to predict the spall liner performance of structural composites in terms of the behind armour cone angle resulting from overmatching threats

6.0 Conclusions

A multi-scale modelling approach has been demonstrated that can provide high strain rate material properties for macro scale modelling. Micro and meso scale material models have been developed that take into account damage initiation, damage evolution and strain rate scaling. The modelling work has provided material properties for S2 Glass / epoxy NCF lamina and carbon / epoxy NCF lamina. These properties have been utilized for blast and ballistic modelling.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to acknowledge the financial support of the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council through Nottingham Innovative Manufacturing Research Centre and the Technology Strategy Board through contract reference TP/8/MAT/6/I/Q1576E. Partners in the TSB funded LiMBS project are also thanked for their support.

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